

(Ia), (IIa) : X = H. (Ib), (IIb) : X = - CONH₂

(Ic), (IIIc) : X = - Ph. (Id), (IId) : X = - C₆H₄.F

The ethanolic solution of compound (I), when kept with cold and dilute hydrochloric acid for 2-3 days deposited *p*-fluorobenzeneazoacetic acid (III) which on refluxing with *p*-fluorophenylhydrazine was cyclised to compound (Id). The ethanolic solution of compound (I), however, when heated with dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded *p*-fluorophenylhydrazone of α -ketopropionaldehyde (IV)⁴.

It has been further observed that like sulphanilamidopyrimidines⁵, *p*-fluorobenzene-diazonium chloride also reacted with maleic acid, methylacrylate, crotonic acid, and ethylcrotonate to yield *p*-fluorocinnamic acid (V), β carboxy-*p*-fluorocinnamic acid, (VI), α -chloro- β -methyl-*p*-fluorohydrocinnamic acid (VII), and β -methyl-*p*-fluorocinnamic acid (VIII).

2,4-Dinitrophenylacetone on treatment with diazonium chloride of *p*-fluoroaniline yielded *p*-fluorophenylhydrazone of 1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-1,2-propanedione (IX), which when heated with sodium hydroxide solution was cyclised to 6-nitro-1-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-3-acetylisoindazole (X).⁶

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl p-fluorobenzeneazoacetate (I).—A diazotised solution of *p*-fluoroaniline (1.1 g.) was poured on a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (50 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.), water (25ml) and ethanol (25 ml) and shaken vigorously. A pale yellow crystalline precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from ethanol produced 80% yield of

4. Prakash and Gambhir, this Journal, 1964, 41, 133.

5. Idem, *ibid.*, 1966, 43.

6. Borsche, *Ber.*, 1908, 42, 601.

the ester (I) as golden yellow needles, m.p. 94°. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{12}H_{13}FN_2O_2$ requires N, 11.11%) 2,4-DNP of compound (I) was obtained as orange-red plates, m.p. 234°. (Found: N, 19.28. $C_{18}H_{17}FN_3O_6$ requires N, 19.44%).

By adopting a similar procedure a few more azo derivatives have been prepared and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

*Compounds	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen		2,4-DNP m.p.
					Found	Reqd.	
Methyl-FB-acetoacetate	97°	Golden yellow	80%	$C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_2F$	11.49	11.76	246°
Ethyl-FB-benzoylacetate	104°	Lemon-yellow	83	$C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_2F$	18.73	8.91	237°
FB-acetyl-acetone (II)	117°	Yellow	85	$C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2F$	12.38	12.61	248°
FB-benzoylacetone	81°	Pale yellow	85	$C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_2F$	9.63	9.85	226°
FB- <i>n</i> -benzoyl-acetophenone	121°	Golden yellow	87	$C_{21}H_{15}O_2N_2F$	7.94	8.09	249°

*FB denotes "*p*-fluorobenzeneazo."

3-Methyl-4-(*p* fluorobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (Ia).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g.) were heated for 1 hr. On cooling and adding water a yellow precipitate separated. This on recrystallization from ethanol furnished 70% of the product as yellow needles, m.p. 207°. (Found: N, 25.14. $C_{10}H_9FN_4O$ requires N, 25.45%).

Other pyrazolones and their derivatives, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

*Compounds	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
3-Methyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	207°	Golden yellow	70%	$C_{10}H_9ON_4F$	25.20	25.45
3-Phenyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	186°	Yellow	65	$C_{15}H_{11}ON_4F$	19.09	19.85
3,5-Dimethyl-4-FB-pyrazole (IIa)	193°	Pale yellow	65	$C_{11}H_{11}N_4F$	25.34	25.68
3-Methyl-4-FB-5-phenylpyrazole	200°	Dirty yellow	70	$C_{16}H_{15}N_4F$	19.77	20.00
3,5-Diphenyl-4-FB-pyrazole	211°	Lemon-yellow	65	$C_{21}H_{15}N_4F$	16.18	16.37

*As recorded in Table I.

3-Methyl-4-(*p* fluorobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amide (Ib).—A solution of compound I (2.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g.) and sodium acetate

(0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hrs. On adding water, the precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 198°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 26.24. $C_{11}H_{10}FN_2O_2$ requires N, 26.61%).

Other pyrazolone and pyrazole-1-amide derivatives, prepared as above, are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

1-Amides of FB*	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.
3-Methyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	106°	Pale yellow	70%	$C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_2F$	26.43	26.61
3-Phenyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	211°	Yellow	65	$C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2F$	21.31	21.53
3,5-Dimethyl-4-FB-pyrazole (IIb)	207°	Do	70	$C_{10}H_{12}ON_2F$	26.59	26.82
3-Methyl-4-FB-5-phenylpyrazole	215°	Lemon-yellow	65	$C_{17}H_{14}ON_2F$	21.34	21.67
3,5-Diphenyl-4-FB-pyrazole	210°	Yellow	65	$C_{22}H_{16}ON_2F$	19.01	18.18

*As recorded in Table I.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(*p*-fluorobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (Ic).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and phenylhydrazine (1.0 g.) was heated for 2 hrs. and then cooled. The solid separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in orange needles in 75% yield, m.p. 140°. (Found: N, 18.73. $C_{16}H_{13}FN_4O$ requires N, 18.91%).

A few phenylpyrazolone and pyrazole derivatives, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Compounds 4-(<i>p</i> -fluorobenzeneazo)	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.
1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	140°	Orange	75%	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_4F$	18.70	18.91
1,3-Diphenyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	163°	Red	70	$C_{21}H_{15}ON_4F$	15.45	15.44
1-Phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-FB-pyrazole (IIc)	151°	Do	70	$C_{17}H_{15}N_4F$	18.67	19.04
1,5-Diphenyl-3-methyl-4-FB-pyrazole	172°	Orange-red	65	$C_{20}H_{17}N_4F$	15.58	15.75
1,3,5-Triphenyl-4-FB-pyrazole	169°	Do	65	$C_{27}H_{19}N_4F$	13.21	13.69

*'FB' same as recorded in Table I.

1-(*p*-Fluorophenyl)-3-methyl-4-(*p*-fluorobenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (Id) was prepared from *p*-fluorophenylhydrazine and compound (I). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 70% yield as reddish plates, m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 17.67. $C_{16}H_{12}F_2N_4O$ requires N, 17.83%).

Other *p*-fluorophenylpyrazolone and pyrazole derivatives, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Compounds	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.
1-(F)-3-methyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	190°	Orange Red	70%	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₄ F ₂	17.84	17.83
1-(F)-3-phenyl-4-FB-5-pyrazolone	200°	Red	69	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₄ F ₂	14.87	14.86
1-(F)-3,5-dimethyl-4-FB-pyrazole (IId)	188°	Orange	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ F ₂	17.79	17.84
1-(F)-3-methyl-4-FB-5-phenylpyrazole	212°	Orange	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ F ₂	14.68	14.97
1-(F)-3, 5-diphenyl-4-FB-pyrazole	209°	Red	65	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ F ₂	12.70	12.84

NB.—'FB' same. F denotes (*p*-fluorophenyl).

3-Methyl-4-(*p* fluorobenzeneazo)-5-isoxazolone (Io).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 3 hrs. On dilution, the precipitate separating was recrystallised from dilute ethanol in 65% yield as pale-yellow needles, m.p. 187° (Found: N, 18.87. C₁₀H₈FN₂O₂ requires N, 19.00%).

A few isoxazolone and isoxazole derivatives were prepared similarly. These are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI

*Compounds	M.P.	Colour	Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.
4-(<i>p</i> -fluorobenzeneazo)						
3-Methyl-4-FB-5-isoxazolone	187°	Yellow	65%	C ₁₀ H ₈ FN ₂ O ₂	18.85	19.00
3-Phenyl-4-FB-5-isoxazolone	207°	Pale yellow	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ FN ₂ O ₂	14.67	14.84
3,5-Dimethyl-4-FB-isoxazole (IIe)	194°	Lemon yellow	60	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ FN ₂ O	19.00	19.18
3-Methyl-4-FE-5-phenylisoxazole	211°	Yellow	56	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ FN ₂ O	14.77	14.94
3,5-Diphenyl-4-FB-isoxazole	215°	Yellow	56	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O	12.01	12.24

*As recorded in Table I.

p-Fluorobenzeneazoacetic Acid (III).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) and HCl conc., 10 ml was kept for few days. The deposited solid was recrystallised from ethanol in yellow prisms, m.p. 109°, yield 60% (Found: N, 12.29. C₁₀H₈FN₂O₂ requires N, 12.50%).

α -Ketopropionnaldehyde-*p*-fluorophenylhydrazone (IV)—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed with HCl (dil., 30 ml) for 2 hrs. On cooling the yellow precipitate separated was recrystallised from ethanol in golden yellow needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 15.35. $C_9H_7FN_2O$ requires N, 15.55%).

p-Fluorocinnamic Acid (V): *Method A*.—The diazotised solution of *p*-fluoroaniline (1.2 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of maleic acid (1.2 g.) containing cupric chloride (0.6 g.) and sodium acetate (2.5 g.). The mixture so obtained, was stirred maintaining the temperature at 40°. On keeping it overnight, a brown solid was deposited; it was recrystallised from ethanol in cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 207° yield 5%. (Found: C, 64.78, H, 4.12. $C_9H_7FO_2$ requires C, 65.06; H, 4.21%).

Method B.—Acetic acid (3.0 ml) was neutralised with 40% NaOH solution and then mixed with cupric chloride (0.6 g.) and an acetone solution of methyl acrylate (0.9 g.). To it was added *p*-fluorobenzenediazonium chloride (1.2 g.) with stirring and warming to 40° till no more nitrogen had evolved. On keeping overnight the brown mass separating was dissolved in EtOH-NaOH (20 ml, 10%) and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The precipitate obtained on acidification was recrystallised from ethanol to yield the acid (V). Its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of the acid remained undepressed.

β -Carboxy-*p*-fluorocinnamic acid (VI) prepared by the procedure adopted for compound (V) (*Method A*), keeping pH 1, was recrystallised from ethanol in 20% yield in lemon yellow needles, m.p. 166°. (Found: C, 57.00, H, 3.08. $C_{10}H_7FO_4$ requires C, 57.14; H, 3.33%).

α -Chloro- β -methyl-*p*-fluorohydrocinnamic Acid (VII).—The diazotised solution of *p*-fluoroaniline (1.2 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of crotonic acid (0.9 g.) containing cupric chloride and sodium acetate. The product was recrystallised from ethanol in 14% yield as cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 197°. (Found: C, 55.19, H, 4.47. $C_{10}H_{10}ClFO_2$ requires C, 55.42; H, 4.62%).

β -Methyl-*p*-fluorocinnamic Acid (VIII): *Method A*.—By adopting a similar procedure as for compound (V) (*Method B*), it was prepared by using *p*-fluorobenzenediazonium chloride (1.2 g.) and ethylcrotonate (1.2 g.). The product on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 6% of the product (VIII) as cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 226°. (Found: C, 66.43, H, 4.73. $C_{10}H_9FO_2$ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.06%).

Method B.—A solution of compound (VII) 2.1 g.) in anhydrous alcohol (20 ml) and sodium acetate (2.0 g.) was refluxed for 5 hrs, and the product (VIII) recrystallised from ethanol in 30% yield. The mixed m.p. of compounds prepared by *Methods A and B* remained unchanged.

p-Fluorophenylhydrazone of 1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-1,2-propandione (IX).—A diazotised solution of *p*-fluoroaniline (1.1 g.) was mixed with a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (50 g.), 2,4-dinitrophenylacetone (1.5 g.) ethanol (20 ml), and water (10 ml) and the mixture shaken vigorously. The pale-yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol-acetic acid mixture in orange-yellow prisms, m.p. 210° yield 76%. (Found: N, 16.04. $C_{17}H_{11}FN_4O_5$ required N, 16.18%).

2,4-DNP of compound (IX) was obtained as orange-plates, m.p. 256°. (Found: N, 21.07. $C_{21}H_{13}FN_6O_5$ requires N, 21.29%).

6-Nitro-1-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-3-acetylisoindazole (X).—The compound (IX) 3.4 g.) was mixed with a 5% solution of NaOH (20ml) and refluxed for 15 min. A dirty white crystalline precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in yellow prisms, m.p. 182°, yield 50%. (Found: N, 13.86. $C_{13}H_{10}FN_3O_3$ requires N, 14.04%).

Phenylhydrazone of compound (X) was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 267°. (Found: N, 17.80 $C_{21}H_{16}FN_3O_2$ requires N, 17.99%).

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